

Studies on catalytic vapour phase ammoxidation of γ -picoline for the production of 4-cyanopyridine

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Abstract : 4-Cyanopyridine has been prepared using silica/zeolite based catalysts. The reaction was carried out at 340–370° with V₂O₅ : P₂O₅ : MoO₃ : SiO₂ (1 : 0.05 : 0.30 : 13 mole ratio) and at 340–425° with V₂O₅ : P₂O₅ : MoO₃ : H-ZSM-5 (1 : 0.125 : 3.209 : 1.683 wt. ratio) catalyst systems.

Keywords : γ -Picoline, 4-cyanopyridine, ammoxidation.

γ -Picoline on ammoxidation gives 4-cyanopyridine which is an important step in the large scale production of isonicotinamide and isonicotinic acid hydrazide. Ammoxidation of picoline got importance because of cyanopyridines formed in this process can be rapidly hydrolysed to obtain good yield of free pyridine carboxylic acids or their amides which are widely used in drug industries¹. Although binary combination of V₂O₅ with chromium and molybdenum or titanium is very active and selective towards the ammoxidation of picolines, silica/zeolite catalyst system is cheaper, easily available and has high activity and selectivity. So silica/zeolite catalyst has been selected due to its low cost, easy availability and selectivity of the catalyst is also high.

Results and discussion

At lower temperature the percentage yield of 4-cyanopyridine is less and the yield is found to decrease at

higher temperature (Table 1) with a maximum at 350°. On the other hand highest conversion of γ -picoline was found to be at the temperature range 345–350° and the highest conversion was found to be at the mole ratio of γ -picoline : NH₃ : O₂ (1 : 6 : 13) at the temperature 350° using the system V₂O₅ : P₂O₅ : MoO₃ : SiO₂. Higher the mole ratio of air, greater the percentage loss of γ -picoline. At the mole ratio of γ -picoline : NH₃ : O₂ :: 1 : 6 : 10 the yield is maximum. With the catalyst system V₂O₅ : P₂O₅ : MoO₃ : H-ZMS-5 (Table 2) (1 : 0.125 : 3.209 : 1.683) for the ammoxidation of γ -picoline to 4-cyanopyridine the percentage yield of 4-cyanopyridine increases with the increase in temperature and at the temperature range of 350–360° the percentage yield is reasonably constant. Highest yield in found to decrease gradually above 375°. The maximum conversion of γ -picoline was found to be at the temperature range 400–425° by using the system V₂O₅ : P₂O₅ : MoO₃ : H-ZMS-5.

Table I. Effects of temperature on V₂O₅ : P₂O₅ : MoO₃ : SiO₂ (1 : 0.05 : 0.30 : 13) catalyst

React. temp. (°C)	Mole ratio γ -picoline : NH ₃ : O ₂	Contact time (s)	Unreacted γ -picoline (%)	Conversion of γ -picoline (%)	Yield (%)
340	1 : 6 : 10	0.79	76.43	23.57	49.8
345	1 : 6 : 10	1.55	69.22	30.78	52.37
350	1 : 6 : 10	0.77	71.54	28.46	80.39
355	1 : 6 : 10	0.79	86.24	13.76	53.05
360	1 : 6 : 10	1.71	79.71	20.29	28.69
370	1 : 6 : 10	1.75	77.08	22.92	21.29

Table 2. Effects of temperature on $V_2O_5 : P_2O_5 : MoO_3 : H\text{-ZSM-5}$ (1 : 0.125 : 3.209 : 1.683 wt. ratio)

React. temp. (°C)	Mole ratio γ -picoline : $NH_3 : O_2$	Space velocity		Contact time ^c (s)	Unreacted γ -picoline (%)	Conversion of γ -picoline (%)	Yield (%)
		WHSV ^a	GHSV ^b				
340	1 : 7 : 8.6	0.347	2478	1.45	58.45	41.55	43.53
350	1 : 6 : 7.5	0.399	2468	1.45	54.96	45.04	65.56
360	1 : 6 : 7.7	0.389	2452	1.46	61.70	38.30	67.45
375	1 : 6 : 7.9	0.388	2446	1.5	73.38	26.62	70.13
400	1 : 6 : 7	0.416	2475	1.45	48.80	51.20	51.00
425	1 : 6.2 : 7	0.409	2706	1.33	52.05	47.95	49.03

^aWHSV = Weight hourly space velocity, ^bGHSV = gas hourly space velocity, ^ccontact time = 3600 s/GHSV.

Conclusion : From the comparative study silica support is best for ammoxidation of γ -picoline.

Experimental

The following catalysts were prepared for the ammoxidation of γ -picoline.

$V_2O_5 : P_2O_5 : MoO_3 : SiO_2$ (1 : 0.55 : 0.30 : 13 mole ratio) catalyst : Silica impregnated with required amount of vanadyl oxalate, ammonium molybdate solution and phosphoric acid were placed in a furnace for 4 h (400°) in a silica crucible. It was dried and again placed in a muffle furnace for 3 h at 450°.

$V_2O_5 : P_2O_5 : MoO_3 : H\text{-ZSM-5}$ catalyst (1 : 0.125 : 3.209 : 1.683 wt. ratio) : The same procedure as outlined above was adopted. Instead of silica, H-ZSM-5 was taken as support.

The reactor (pyrex glass tube, 30 cm \times 20 mm i.d.) consisted of two sections, the preheater zone packed with a known weight of catalyst. The two zones are heated in a tubular furnace. The product recovery unit comprised of ice cooler container, spiral traps as well as a number of glass bubblers containing a known volume of saturated solution of boric acid to absorb entire of unreacted ammonia. The liberated gas was passed through different bubbler containing carbon tetrachloride to absorb the vapour of 4-cyanopyridine and pyridine bases. The gas stream is also passed through the known amount of satu-

rated KOH solution, kept in a bubbler to absorb carbon dioxide. A definite amount of catalyst (7.5–20 g) was charged in a reactor placed in a vertical furnace. When the temperature of the catalyst bed was steady then the feed was introduced into the reactor through feeding system along with air and ammonia. The products consisted of 4-cyanopyridine, unreacted γ -picoline, water, carbon dioxide and unreacted ammonia, which were estimated by spectroscopic and other physical methods.

Identification of 4-cyanopyridine : The reaction mixture obtained from the ammoxidation of γ -picoline was extracted with CCl_4 . The CCl_4 layer was dried and CCl_4 was removed in vacuum. About 2 g CCl_4 was hydrolysed with NaOH at reflux temperature for one hour. The reaction mixture was steam distilled to remove unreacted γ -picoline. The residue left after steam distillation was acidified with dil. HCl, then a white precipitate of isonicotinic acid was obtained. The acid was filtered and recrystallised from warm water. Decolourisation was effected with active charcoal. The melting point was identified with that of an authentic sample. Detection and estimation of 4-cyanopyridine and unreacted γ -picoline were further confirmed by IR (Perkin-Elmer FTIR-1720X, UK) and GC techniques (6810, Chemito, India).

Reference

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